

- “When you have eliminated all which is impossible, then whatever remains, however improbable, must be the truth.”¹
- “It is a capital mistake to theorize before one has data. Insensibly one begins to twist facts to suit theories, instead of theories to suit facts.”²

MESS 0025

MIMS 2.10.1-.5 - Sir Arthur Doyle’s Gift: Investigation, the MIMS of empirical observation

Investigation - Observation - Empiricism

Sf. R. Careaga, BSEE, MSTOM

October 2022

ABSTRACT

The issue of the Day is the attempt in our Unlightenment to undo empiricism, rationality, logic, etc. In light of this the author has identified an example of Enlightenment-era MIMS which creates strong springboards for discussion of reality, observation, empiricism, and investigation. Ancillary to this the paper discusses Hindu and Chinese concepts related to the issues of focus and concentration, delusion, etc. The paper finishes with seeking context as a matrix, and as a MIMS for another springboard as a MIMS, in the continuous search for Truth and reality.

Keywords: Sherlock Holmes - Doyle - Truth - Empiricism - Investigation - Illusion - Context

The Great Enlightenment	2
The Uncanny MIMSicality of Sir Doyle	2
Sherlock Holmes, the 1st Modern Superhero	3
The Science of Deduction (MIMS 2.10.31)	3
Forensic Science (MIMS 2.10.32)	4
Observation (MIMS 2.10.1)	5
“The Funnel of F.O.C.U.S.” (MIMS 2.10.13)	6
Empiricism (MIMS 2.10.2)	7
Investigation (MIMS 2.10.3)	7
Quantized Fact (MIMS 2.10.4)	8
Context as a Matrix as a MIMS (MIMS 2.10.5)	8
Conclusion	9
MIMS 2.10.13 continued...	9
References	10

¹ “The Case-Book of Sherlock Holmes.”

² “A Scandal in Bohemia.”

The Great Enlightenment

The GE, if we must assign a date, either began with Benjamin Franklin's kite experiment, in 1752, or Lombe's continuous mill, 1718-21. The latter is definitely the start of the Industrial Revolution. If we are to politely define the GE as the IR+Reformation+Age of Exploration, then either date is in the midst of this period. But many consider the AoE to end in the 1600s, replaced with the Colonial Expansion era. Slavery was ending in 1834 in the British Empire, and this is a product of the GE's reformation and consciousness-expanding properties (including new drug use).

Therefore, let us assign the GE to begin with electrification, as early as 1752, or 1800 (Volta's experiment³). We can definitely say that it ended by 1927 when somehow the mainstream chose Einstein's word about a Bishop's hypothesis with little evidence - Big Bang - over a cosmology that was a product of experimentation throughout the 1800s and early 1900s. All the more mysterious is Einstein's choice given his Nobel was for the photoelectric effect, and Relativity itself began with the Lorentzian Transformation of Maxwell's equations, which Poincare abandoned since one cannot divide by 0.⁴ Nevertheless, though the scientist that discovered the covalent bond, and had a Nobel, named Plasma cosmology, on the backbone of classical electromagnetism, the mainstream abandoned solid empiricism and lab work (like Birkeland's, Langmuir's, and Bostick's) for the power of either quantum weirdness (to make you famous), or General Relativity (to make you rich.)

It was in this period **from 1752 to 1927** that we can pin down perhaps the greatest expansion of human consciousness in a non-philosophical arena, since the engineers that designed the Great Pyramid power plant at least 5,000 years ago (300+ years *prior to* Khufu, according to most recent dating⁵), possibly 13,000 years ago⁶ (Bauval⁷). At any rate, from then to now, there's been little for mankind but occasional blazing trails in the darkness. Much advances in some aspects of philosophy, but mostly in law, farming, and art, and a long struggle to advance or lift the stone of medicine. Outside of this, save architectural wonders that are more art than pure engineering, there was not much to speak of. Paper. That's the advancement that seems to win every award previous to capitalism!

The Uncanny MIMSicality of Sir Doyle

It is in this backdrop of understanding the uniqueness of the period that we find also: a singular mimsical experience. In the mid-late 1800s, there were several sudden alterations in the Victorian landscape. While the Americas were still wild west and recently had a Civil War, struggling with the Democrats not allowing the passage of the Civil Rights Act of 1871⁸, in the British Royal Society and ancillary theatres of science, there were sudden advances in chemistry, optics, new methods of spectroscopy, and in electromagnetism. There were evidences that light was discretely quantized⁹, and that invisible wireless "Hertzian" (now radio) waves¹⁰ were filling the world up. In fact, the true atomic model was about to be discovered¹¹, and as this happened mankind created electrical amusements, Edison made the lightbulb, the telegraph met the phonograph and

³ <https://www.aps.org/publications/apsnews/200603/history.cfm>

⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/History_of_special_relativity

⁵ MAJOR DISCOVERY: Lost Wooden Relic of the Great Pyramid of Giza Found + RADIOCARBON DATED!

⁶ https://www.researchgate.net/publication/327424078_Great_Pyramids_of_Kentucky_-_Final

⁷ <https://www.amazon.com/Orion-Mystery-Unlocking-Secrets-Pyramids/dp/0517884542>

⁸ <https://www.ojp.gov/ncjrs/virtual-library/abstracts/review-civil-rights-act-1871-42-usc-1983-correctional-personnel>

⁹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Photon#Historical_development

¹⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Radio_wave

¹¹ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/atomic-models>

telephony was invented. Then came the combustion engine, powered flight, radios (and crystal-powered¹² ones later), and of course, finally early televisions and the descriptions of computers.

But before any of this, one man set out to explain the Age of Reason to common readers. To explain to people whose lives were changing by leaps and bounds, almost overnight in some cases, with marvelous new wonders powered with invisible stuff called “electricity.” These people were on the edge of actually believing in the ‘fiddle-faddle’ of recent Lockian and Hegelian philosophers, and decided to actually be free (in Europe) like those wild Americans! Americans were “getting it done” but in stuffy little England, Sir Doyle¹³ was writing *murder* mysteries where the world’s first non-mythic **superhero**, Sherlock Holmes¹⁴, was not only taking drugs but using “The Science of Deduction”¹⁵ to discern impossible, scrutable details from crime scenes, and ‘save the day.’ He was uncanny, unflappable, and strangely likable. He was, after all, the “origin of modern forensic science.”¹⁶

Sherlock Holmes, the 1st Modern Superhero

Of course, the man from 221B Baker Street, whose likeness has been played by dozens of men¹⁷ since the early days of film, did not call it forensic science. He simply knew it as deduction, or applied thinking. In fact, he asserted that the people around him almost never thought, but merely made conjectural guesses about how their world worked. Particularly Inspector Lestrade, his collegial nemesis and benefactee.

As a matter of fact, Sherlock Holmes used drugs not to discern better, but to cope and rest his mind, which was - as the engines of industry at the time - ever at work on a new and pressing matter. He was both a literal metaphor and a mimsical expression of the era. He was an embodiment of the feeling of the time that Science would override the irrational, darkness of the human soul - even perhaps Original Sin¹⁸ - and that mankind could reach a level of newfound goodness. In fact, perhaps even a form of perfection, based in scientific rationalism, and even technological progress. This was the beginning of marketing on an industrial level, and of (unfortunately), industrialized materialism. Of course the beginning of this downfall was when multiple roots were laid for a plastic, shallow, divided society infiltrated with Pre-Enlightenment, Pre-Electrified society values, but we digress.

Sherlock did not see all of this progress as remotely regressive. In fact, he saw every bit of it, from the technology to new sciences, catalogs, travel opportunities, down to the types of stock paper he could feel and memorize, as well as forms of chemico-medicinal sciences, as means for expressing the utmost art of his Science of Deduction as the world’s first “consulting detective.”

The Science of Deduction (MIMS 2.10.31)

This is a particular kind of rationality, the long utmost efforts of many great (and perhaps arguably wasted) minds of men of the past. Whether they were limited by vision (Aristotle), scope (Ptolemy), technological opportunity (Baker), or religion (Copernicus), these men - and probably some women - were unable to think to *their utmost*. It is, as has become later believed in the age of neuroscience, that mankind uses such a finite % of their total brainpower, as to be an unbelievable waste. But with Sherlock, Sir Doyle had

¹² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Crystal_radio

¹³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Arthur_Conan_Doyle

¹⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sherlock_Holmes

¹⁵ <https://thescienceofdeduction-co-uk.tumblr.com/> & <https://www.thescienceofdeduction.org/>

¹⁶ <https://www.britannica.com/science/forensic-science>

¹⁷ Though none, and the author is adamant on this, will ever replace the quality and perfection of the portrayal by Jeremy Brett. Absolutely iconic.

¹⁸ Which, due to Darwin’s work being mischaracterized, began “freeing” mankind of the shackles of Genesis.

a perfect MIMS to express this not as disappointment, but as the antithesis of the Dark Ages: pure rationalism based in the minute investigation into the minutia of “details.” After all, “the Devil is in the details.”

So what was the “Science of Deduction?” It is nothing more than applied rationalism and logic, to a chain of evidence - what we now call forensics - combined with pure use of raw data and databases (such as where they were at the time, in the forms of encyclopedias, archived newspapers, and “mind palaces,” etc.) These deductions, made link by link, became a chain that tied perpetrators to their crimes via physical evidence. The physicality equates to the reality - the realion of the previous MESSy¹⁹ - that is involved in any investigation. The criminal wants to cover their crime, and attempts to place obstructions in the way. The investigator - Sherlock - who is representative of all of Science, pursues the Truth through relentless, tireless obsession with “the facts” which must precede (and not be preceded by) *a priori* theories. This is incredibly important. Also, as suggested, the total sum of **all of the facts** must be taken into account. While, “detective inspector” Lestrade represents the *philosophizer*, who takes logical stabs in the dark (Plato’s Cave) We call these ‘theories’ mere conjecture, while the summary of the ‘cogitus modus operandi’ is “elementary”... Dr. Watson meanwhile plays the part of the educated (and martial) literati who watches on in awe and wonder as the hero not only becomes a better man, but makes Mankind better.

Even idyllic and despite all flaws: the perfect consummation of the human mind’s rationality and its foibles. There are, of course, many things to be said about Sherlock’s love affairs - or lack thereof - but let us merely note that in this arena he is a reflection of the Newtonian and Teslan bent: a man not homosexual, but considering himself either too superior for women (and therefore married to his work) or too inferior, for *She* with perfection and grace must exist elsewhere, if she be not in *his* arms. This, of course, may be the mystical (MIMS 2.2) expression of the Mysterious Female, or quite literally the ideals of Victorian London in the 1880s-1910s. Nevertheless, Sherlock is all of these consummations, and the Science of Deduction is the means by which he experiences coitus with the Universe, rather than love/sex. He seeks the *mystery*, and has his orgasm of mind which leads to pure gnosis, and then it saves lives. The closer he gets to cold rationality, the less lovable he is, but when he finishes his work, we love him all the more and look up to him thrice as high. Ergo: he is love, personified, via another route.

Forensic Science (MIMS 2.10.32)

This is particularly interesting because women dominate the field, making up 56-70% of careers²⁰ and enrollments²¹ in forensic science work. Women are particularly good at this science, among other STEM options, because of their attention to details concerning violence. While women are less strong at the high ends of logic and reason, with men dominating the upper echelons of banking, law, strategy, chess, and STEM top-level research and programs, women are doing extremely excellent in many of these fields. One day they may account for the bulk volume of these other fields, as they do with forensic science and research. For now, we can only speculate as to the cultural reasons, but part and parcel of it has to be how “Sherlocked” women tend to be on this. He is a) young, b) sexy (as a pure male brain), c) sophisticated, d) heroic, e) pure (he never hits women and is **always** a courteous gentleman), and f) a bit metrosexual. Women confide in him throughout the series, even though he is actually not empathizing but eliciting their stories out (teasing them out) to a great degree. Dr. Watson plays the actual empathizer and coddles their feelings. Eventually he marries one of the women from the case solved by Sherlock.

¹⁹ MIMS 2.21 - MESS0024: Engineering MIMS Philosophy into a Plug and Play Platform (P7 Resolution)

²⁰ <https://www.zippia.com/forensic-scientist-jobs/demographics/>

²¹ <https://www.psu.edu/news/research/story/probing-question-do-women-dominate-field-forensic-science/>

He is also a quintessential item: a bad boy. He does drugs, practices a rare form of martial art Bartitsu²² (portrayed using Wing Chun in the Downey big-screen version), has an elusive female ‘bad girl’ girlfriend (*The Woman*²³), and is, after all, cooler than a cop and as a “high functioning sociopath” (Cumberbatch portrayal) is flawed in a way that increases his appeal. How can he be fixed? No female will ever know. He can’t. And that’s extremely lovable or at least desireable/sexy.

But, what about the science? What is so mimsical for women about *this* science? Well this is not a mystery: the majority of victims of murders in spousal abuse situations are women.²⁴ Women want to be heroines, too. There’s nothing mysterious about this. What is unique, is the choice of STEMM field here is so clearly related to a “do-gooder” mentality. The appeal is to be cold and rational, so that one cannot be touched by the bloody circumstances. Shows about murder and mysteries (like “Unsolved Mysteries”) are far more popular with women²⁵. It could be a dream field for many. Certainly, the male aesthetic or fantasy for this is more of a Detective Hanna²⁶ (“Heat”) who is sharp, fast, witty, alpha, and sexually frustrated. He carries his “angst” with him to keep him sharp, and does cocaine (“Heat 2”) to be even sharper. The noir schtick is more mimsical for the male brain.

But while men fantasize about being the sharpshooter, sleuth-negotiator who is completely “in control”... there is something oddly alien and appealing about the hero of the variety of Holmes. We are meant to identify with Dr. Watson (or for Victorian women, with his fiance and later wife). But we are meant to *aspire to be* Sherlock Holmes. Watching him solve a mystery is particularly inspiring, that’s for sure.

The science he produces, therefore, requires us to “stop and ask for directions...” and what man wants to do that? As we shall see in a future MESSy review of an altstream interview gone wrong, where the EPEMC standards were not being applied (by not the author but R. Burke²⁷), there is a major flaw in male-dominated science as it exists: too few men stop and *Sherlock* the situation. They mostly do the opposite of the Science of Deduction: they guess, based on a hunch. Based on *conjecture*. Science isn’t noir. Your gut is irrelevant. Facts, then theories. Not theories and make-up facts to suit them.

In the words of Ben Shapiro, “Facts don’t care about your feelings.”

Observation (MIMS 2.10.1)

The key issue, the author *thinks*, from his own observations about the failures in logic and reasoning (See: MESSy 31) is that people fail to observe most things. There are six awarenesses in self-defense²⁸, and all of them are based on Observations. In the author’s thinking, Observation is about *perception*, combined with concentration and focus. This, the author is sure of: that few people observe with their third eye, and most are deluded with their two ocular lenses by the gunas²⁹, skandhas³⁰, and maya³¹. Ultimately they are usually increasing, not decreasing their *dukkha*³² (ignorant suffering).

²² <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bartitsu>

²³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Irene_Adler

²⁴ <https://ncadv.org/STATISTICS>

²⁵ <https://www.vogue.in/culture-and-living/content/why-are-women-obsessed-with-true-crime-stories>

²⁶ https://die-hard-scenario.fandom.com/wiki/Vincent_Hanna

²⁷ MESS0036: Responding to Burke’s Himalaya-Comet YDE hypothesis

²⁸ NAILS (brochure)

²⁹ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gu%E1%B9%87a>

³⁰ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Skandha>

³¹ [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Maya_\(religion\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Maya_(religion))

³² <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Du%E1%B8%A5kha>

“The Funnel of F.O.C.U.S.³³” (MIMS 2.10.13)

The difference between focus and concentration is not trivial, in the philosophæther. Focus is an ocular shrinkage in the diameter of the foci or “hole” through which things are seen. Concentration is an anti-dilution or increase in density about the subject. How we observe also appears to have an ætheric effect upon the particle-matter in the atomic mass-energy (AME). “What does it even matter?” Well, we see that matter is the AME, and AME is plasma-electromagnetic, even Unified Aether Field related. The UAF is therefore the “spiritual” while the AME is the “material” (literally) in the MIMS relationship:

$$\star \text{ UAF} \rightleftharpoons \text{PEMF} \rightleftharpoons \text{AME} \quad \rightarrow \quad \text{Counterspace} \rightleftharpoons \text{Aether (A power)} \rightleftharpoons \text{Space} \quad (1)$$

In this observation, we see that clearly the main issue of Power is related not only through the *P* power, and therefore physics (aka natural philosophæ) and therefore guided by our *philosophæther*, but that the oculus through which we detect, measure, surmise from, etc. all has an incredible part to play in the actualization, the “realion” (or crystalized/Fated³⁶ moment), of the PPPC³⁷.

Empiricism (MIMS 2.10.2)

This is the reason why empiricism is king, while all subjectivism - all of it - is inferior to it. What God projects (via the “Big G”) downwards, just as the MIMS 1.0 diagram suggests, we must either accept or rebel against. Rejection is **not** an option. You cannot reject gravity, or chemistry, or death. You cannot reject the law, anymore than you can reject Causality and Causation itself. What you can do is refuse to accept, and this is termed “rebellion.”

³³ Follow One Course Until Successful ... in this case at finding Truth.

³⁴ https://www.academia.edu/86922819/Structure_of_the_Uni_Multiverse_pre_EPEMC

³⁵ “If you know the enemy and know yourself, you need not fear the result of a hundred battles. If you know yourself but not the enemy, for every victory gained you will also suffer a defeat. If you know neither the enemy nor yourself, you will succumb in every battle.” ~Sun Tzu

³⁶ f region https://www.academia.edu/84913012/MIMS_2_2_5_2_The_Five_forces_that_Influence_Life

³⁷

https://www.academia.edu/50901241/MIMS_2_1_1_2_Aether_Business_and_Analytics_With_a_short_reflection_upon_the_philosophies_of_Ayn_Rand_and_the_concepts_of_Fortune_as_it_relates_to_the_Aether

Empiricism protects us from stupid, ignorant decisions. Drinking drano or antifreeze is self-obvious to most people, but it isn't to a cat. Isn't that just as bad as the Bible's warning, "There's a way that seems right to a man, that leads only unto death?" It is just as bad. They represent the same anti-mimsical aspect. They represent *denial* of empirical observation. For Lestrade to argue with Sherlock by attacking the Science of Deduction, is not to support religion but *superstition*. The True Religion³⁸ is equivocal to the True Science.

❖ True Science ↔ True Religion (2)

Investigation (MIMS 2.10.3)

The heart of the Science of Deduction - as Sherlock practices it, or as it is meant to be practiced - is found not simply in empirical observation. That isn't a disparagement on the other two MIMS. But investigation is special. It involves the word *invest*, which has economic implications, and energetic overtures. It implies work, and it also implies a charge relationship. Etymologically,

*"a searching into, a searching for," noun of action from past participle stem of investigare "to trace out, search after,"*³⁹

What would one be searching after... sniffing out? Mysteries. What is science generally for? Discovering mysteries, and eliminating bad explanations for those mysteries; while hopefully elucidating actual, factual answers.

So we see the meaning of deep investment of energy and time, and the near perpetual searching out of the mystery, sticking evidence parcel by evidence parcel, and piecing it together in a chain. The stronger the links, the stronger the truth. The hope that in the end, a tension develops between the end of the chain: the crime or mystery, and the hand holding the facts. With this chain, the wily beast of ignorance, slavery, suffering, delusion, and that which makes us lost in the forest, alone... is reeled in. Reigned. Conquered. Eventually, these mysteries are removed all in all, leaving only enlightenment based on cold, rational fact.

Investigations often reveal dirty truths, and dirty truths people want to hide reveal lies. The lies of antiquity and organized religion, of secret societies, etc., are obstructionist to the discoveries of those things which *inspired* those early religions, well before they became organized and bureaucratic. What powerful families, chiefs, and religions hid behind a form of "paywall" turned out to be the most important bits of human history. What was propped up, the royal families and their pomp and circumstance and supposed ties to the star Lord, to the messiahs and farming, etc., turned out to be the lesser information, scientifically speaking. Cosmonogically, though, all of it became fairly helpful in our own quest and search for the "ultimate answers." The only way to do that, is to chase down every lead, and investigate every opportunity. No stone left unturned, so to speak. And this - Holmes' **relentlessness** - above all else is his hallmark trait.

Quantized Fact (MIMS 2.10.4)

Evidence is not new. In Jesus' trial, even, the Jews had [false] evidence, and in the Commandments it is said to be a sin to "bear false witness." Hence the need for not simply evidence: but for *data*. "In veritas, vino."⁴⁰ In the philosophæther, we mean the dæther⁴¹. We mean that data can not only be captured, cataloged, and logged, but potentially modeled as gaseous plasma in vacuum. Or perhaps the plasma is in a fluid

³⁸ "The Three Fold Science" or "Sacred Science", etc. , not to be confused with the *New Religion*. <https://bit.ly/3lsecCl>

³⁹ <https://www.etymonline.com/word/investigation>

⁴⁰ Truth is wine; a spin on the original.

⁴¹ https://www.academia.edu/67236577/MIMS_2_102_In_pursuit_of_the_Daether

solution? What is not clear, is not only how and where the data constructs of principles and formulas are stored (in the Law of Conservation).

However, what is clear is that the data is the bridge between the *N* and *A* powers, indicating that dæthereal involvement in evidence is going to strengthen our connection between fact and possibility. And the annulus of Fate - of reality and the virtual [philosophical] particle of the realion - is contracted around fewer and fewer threads, until only one remains: the true one. The true thread of data, the quantum stream, collapsing to a singular fact, inescapable by any means of sophistry or misapplied logic, then binds the circumstantial to the concrete dictums of It All. Causation consummates, and the laws are set into motion revolving about this fact.

The more quantized, or numericalized, therefore, the more factual. Such that we can define factness vs "truthiness" along a simple axis of more to less investigation of the basis of fact. Thus the need for liars and conspirators to cover up events and data, to hide things. From 9/11 to COVID to The Gulf of Tonkin, and anything in between or more... business scandals and personal affairs... we see that people will hide evidence and data. Particularly data when they do NOT want Truth to be set free.

Ergo it is clear that investigation, as a MIMS sets Truth free, and this sets us free. So one can almost say that the key to all fact-finding is the use of the triplicated ocularis, the mind's eye and the eyes that can be easily fooled. Did "God" give us the 3rd eye to prevent being fooled? Unknowable. But if that mind's eye is not applied with critical thinking to the very task of thinking, of deducing, of researching and investigation, then it will be increasingly deluded. Nescience is antithetical to science. Dukkha is an anti-MIMS, naturally. But particularly when it is increased by willful ignorance.

Context as a Matrix as a MIMS (MIMS 2.10.5)

Every matrix has a parenthetical region of validity, we shall call it context. And the use of this context, itself, is a matrix. It is an automatic 2x1 array, if not 3x1. One of the positions involves the fact of, and the other the facts against. Both provide truth. But this tinier matrix gives not only context but a framework for finding more truth. There is a trail coming from either position in the array, and there's more ability to find more data, more Truth. This, by definitions as we marked above, is mimsical. One increases humanity's positional Shi if

one increases truth, bit by bit. That improves human life and if not at first, happiness; it also reveals more layers in the fractal superstructure, etc. How can that, if it begets a mentality of loving or at least improving the superstructure (usually Nature, perhaps Science, definitely Society) not be MIMSical? The very act of bringing forth Truth from obscurity into the Light might be completely central to the *plot* or "meaning of Life." That,

above all, is definitely MIMSical.

“This above all: to thine own self be true, And it must follow, as the night the day, Thou canst not then be false to any man.” ~Shakespeare, “Hamlet”

Conclusion

The importance in science, mainstream or altstream, of investigation - of empiricism - is not to be underestimated. In fact, it is of absolute vitality, and is 100% MIMSical. There is something unique about Sir Doyle’s creation, both of non-mythic superheroes and of forensic science. He created not only the ideal science, but the idyllic man. He created a [pre-Campbellian] timeless character, because Truth and deductive science, is itself timeless. So is hope. Hope springs eternal, and mankind’s hope in fact, in revealed Truth “setting us free” is just as eternal. Or so we may hope, in this age of Unlightenment. We will find out, in time, one way or the other. But will we see through the morass of ignorance, to the clear light of fact, and the gift of observation, focus, and concentration? Will we investigate truth to the utmost core and Truth of ourselves? Or slip back, as they did after Atlantis and the original Egypt, into ages of Darkness and superstitious guessing? Every generation votes with their conscious thoughts and acts. Every click, and tap, and every worship of the electric palm-idols, renews that old test. Investigate *your* circumstances, clearly, and unravel the most important facts of all: your Self-awareness.

“What one man can invent, another can discover.”⁴²

“We balance probabilities and choose the most likely. It is the scientific use of imagination.”⁴³

MIMS 2.10.13 continued...

- Observation
 - Empiricism
 - Investigation
 - Due Diligence
- Concentration
- Focus
- ★ Resolution [DAINED’d-realion]

⁴² “The Dancing Men”

⁴³ “The Great Shadow and Other Napoleonic Tales”

References

1. "March 20, 1800: Volta describes the Electric Battery," APS Physics Volume 15, # 3, E. Tretkoff, 2022, <https://www.aps.org/publications/apsnews/200603/history.cfm>
2. "History of special relativity," Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/History_of_special_relativity
3. "MAJOR DISCOVERY: Lost Wooden Relic of the Great Pyramid of Giza Found + RADIOCARBON DATED!" Youtube/Ancient Architects, 2021, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-NB1XbAUjuA>
4. "Great Pyramids of Kentucky - Final," ResearchGate, Sf. R. Careaga, 2018, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/327424078_Great_Pyramids_of_Kentucky_-_Final
5. "The Orion Mystery: Unlocking the Secrets of the Pyramids," Amazon, R. Bauval & A. Gilbert, 1995, <https://www.amazon.com/Orion-Mystery-Unlocking-Secrets-Pyramids/dp/0517884542>
6. "Review of the Civil Rights Act of 1871 (42 USC 1983) for Correctional Personnel (From Proceedings of the 29th Annual Southern Conference on Corrections," U.S. Department of Justice, J. D. White, 1984, <https://www.ojp.gov/ncjrs/virtual-library/abstracts/review-civil-rights-act-1871-42-usc-1983-correctional-personnel>
7. "Photon," Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Photon#Historical_development
8. "Radio wave," Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Radio_wave
9. "Atomic Models," (EPEMC) Gateway/The Pulse, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/atomic-models>
10. "Crystal radio," Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Crystal_radio
11. "Arthur Conan Doyle," Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Arthur_Conan_Doyle
12. "Sherlock Holmes," Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sherlock_Holmes
13. "The Science of Deduction," Tumblr.com, S. Holmes, <https://thescienceofdeduction-co-uk.tumblr.com/>
14. "Forensic Science," Encyclopedia Britannica, J. A. Siegel, 2020, <https://www.britannica.com/science/forensic-science>
15. "MIMS 2.21 - MESS0024: MIMEngineering MIMS Philosophy into a Plug and Play Platform (P7 Resolution), Academia," Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/89137689/MESS0024_MIMS_2_52_Engineering_the_MIMS_Philosophy_into_a_P_7_Resolution
16. "Forensic Scientist Demographics and Statistics In the US," Zippia.com, <https://www.zippia.com/forensic-scientist-jobs/demographics/>
17. "Probing Question: Do women dominate the field of forensic science?" Penn State, M. Beattie-Moss, 2013, <https://www.psu.edu/news/research/story/probing-question-do-women-dominate-field-forensic-science/>
18. "Bartitsu," Wikipedia, <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bartitsu>
19. "Irene Adler," Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Irene_Adler
20. "Statistics," <https://ncadv.org/STATISTICS>
21. "This might be the reason why women are obsessed with true crime stories," Vogue, M. Sharma, 2020, <https://www.vogue.in/culture-and-living/content/why-are-women-obsessed-with-true-crime-stories>
22. "Vincent Hanna," Wiki Fandom, https://die-hard-scenario.fandom.com/wiki/Vincent_Hanna
23. "MESS0036: Responding to Burke's Himalaya-Comet YDE hypothesis," Sf. R. Careaga, 2022
24. "NAILS: New Approach in Legal Self Defense," https://drive.google.com/file/d/0BwoOz_mUBUfuNzY2YWVhZDFlMTAyYS00OGNmLWI3MTQ0NzUwZDlwNGE4M2Zl/view?resourcekey=0-qO69ueDqK_emLcKTF1AJZw
25. "Guna," Wikipedia, <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gu%E1%B9%87a>
26. "Skandha," Wikipedia, <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Skandha>
27. "Maya (religion)," Wikipedia, [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Maya_\(religion\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Maya_(religion))
28. "Duhkha," Wikipedia, <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Du%E1%B8%A5kha>
29. "Structure of the Uni-Multiverse; pre-EPEMC," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, https://www.academia.edu/86922819/Structure_of_the_Uni_Multiverse_pre_EPEMC
30. "MIMS 2.2.5.2 - The Five "forces" that Influence Life," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/84913012/MIMS_2_2_5_2_The_Five_forces_that_Influence_Life
31. "MIMS 2.1.1-2: Aether, Business & Analytics; With a short reflection upon the philosophies of Ayn Rand and the concepts of Fortune as it relates to the Aether," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, https://www.academia.edu/50901241/MIMS_2_1_1_2_Aether_Business_and_Analytics_With_a_short_reflection_upon_the_philosophies_of_Ayn_Rand_and_the_concepts_of_Fortune_as_it_relates_to_the_Aether
32. "MIMS: The threefold Sacred Sciences," Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, <https://bit.ly/3lsecCl>
33. "Investigation," Online Etymology Dictionary, <https://www.etymonline.com/word/investigation>
34. "MIMS 2.102 - In pursuit of the Daether," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/67236577/MIMS_2_102_In_pursuit_of_the_Daether